

Evaluation of the Diagnostic Efficacy of Magnetic Resonance Imaging in Neurodegenerative Diseases: A Systematic Review of the Literature

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 27 June 2025</p>	<p>Introduction Neurodegenerative diseases, such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's, present complex clinical challenges due to the difficulty in achieving an accurate early diagnosis. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) has proven useful in identifying brain changes before clinical symptoms appear. However, its diagnostic efficacy compared to other methods, such as positron emission tomography (PET), remains under debate.</p> <p>Objective To evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of MRI in neurodegenerative diseases through a systematic review of the literature.</p> <p>Methods A systematic review of systematic reviews and meta-analyses evaluating the diagnostic accuracy of MRI in neurodegenerative diseases was conducted. Studies comparing MRI with other methods, such as CT or biomarkers, were included. Sensitivity, specificity, and ROC curves were assessed.</p> <p>Results Eight studies were included in the review. Structural MRI showed a sensitivity of 73% and a specificity of 71% for early detection of Alzheimer's in patients with mild cognitive impairment. In Parkinson's disease, functional MRI detected functional alterations with a significant reduction in the Amplitude of Low-Frequency Fluctuations in key motor areas. The combination of MRI with PET improved diagnostic accuracy, especially in the early diagnosis of Alzheimer's.</p> <p>Discussion The results highlight the potential of MRI for the early diagnosis of neurodegenerative diseases, although combining it with PET appears to offer greater diagnostic accuracy. Emerging techniques, such as MRI spectroscopy and elastography, could further improve early detection, though more studies are needed to standardize their use.</p>
<p>Corresponding Author: Juan Alzate</p>	<p>KEYWORDS: Magnetic resonance imaging, Neurodegenerative diseases, Diagnostic accuracy, Alzheimer's, Parkinson's.</p>

INTRODUCTION

Neurodegenerative diseases, such as Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, and Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS), present a complex clinical challenge due to their gradual progression and the difficulty of achieving an accurate early diagnosis. Currently, the diagnostic modalities for these pathologies include a combination of clinical evaluation, cerebrospinal fluid biomarkers, and imaging studies, such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and positron emission tomography (PET), which are used to measure the

accumulation of specific proteins like amyloid and tau, associated with Alzheimer's disease (AD) (1). MRI has emerged as a key tool in identifying structural changes in the brain before clinical symptoms appear. In fact, recent MRI analyses have shown that cortical atrophy and reduced white matter volume are related to normal aging and cognitive decline associated with AD. Additionally, the analysis of other parameters such as cortical thickness, surface area, and local gyrification index (LGI) allows for a better characterization of the disease stages and the degree of

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cognitive dysfunction. This suggests that MRI may have advantages for early detection, although its superiority over other methods has not yet been conclusively established (2,3). Despite the increasing use of MRI, the need to clarify its value compared to traditional methods remains critical. Some recent research highlights the use of hybrid modalities, such as PET/MRI, to improve the characterization of neurodegenerative disorders. This approach combines the functional capability of PET with the anatomical resolution of MRI, providing a more comprehensive view of brain pathology and promising an improvement in diagnostic accuracy and early detection (4,5).

Finally, the integration of new MRI sequences, such as T2-weighted imaging and FLAIR imaging, enables the detection of signs of inflammation and changes in white matter, which are relevant to the progression of pathologies like vascular dementia and multiple sclerosis. These technological and methodological developments could increase diagnostic specificity and potentially facilitate earlier and more effective interventions for neurodegenerative diseases. However, variability in techniques and small sample sizes in published studies still pose significant challenges for the generalization of these findings in daily clinical practice.

METHODS

This study was a systematic review that included only previous systematic reviews and meta-analyses evaluating the diagnostic accuracy of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) in neurodegenerative diseases. The objective was to determine whether MRI improves diagnostic accuracy compared to standard diagnostic methods.

Selection Criteria

Systematic reviews and meta-analyses that assessed the diagnostic efficacy of MRI in the context of neurodegenerative diseases were included. Individual studies, clinical trials, or observational studies were not considered unless they were part of a systematic review.

The included studies had to focus on patients with confirmed or suspected neurodegenerative diseases, such as Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, multiple sclerosis, among others. No restrictions were imposed regarding age, sex, or geographic location.

The intervention of interest was the use of MRI as a diagnostic tool compared to other standard diagnostic methods. Comparative methods could include computed tomography (CT), ultrasound, liquid biomarkers, among others.

The primary outcome was diagnostic accuracy, assessed by measures such as sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves.

Secondary outcomes included the clinical utility of MRI in guiding therapeutic decisions, time to diagnosis, and the incidence of incorrect or delayed diagnoses.

Search Methods

Searches were conducted in the following electronic databases:

- PubMed
- EMBASE
- Cochrane Library
- Scopus
- Web of Science

The search terms used included: "magnetic resonance imaging," "neurodegenerative diseases," "diagnostic accuracy," "systematic review," and "meta-analysis." Filters were applied to limit results to systematic reviews and meta-analyses published in the last 10 years.

Reference lists of selected systematic reviews and meta-analyses were manually reviewed to identify additional studies. Conference proceedings and relevant narrative reviews were also explored. No language restrictions were imposed.

Data Collection:

Two independent reviewers evaluated the titles and abstracts of the studies retrieved from the searches. Full texts of potentially relevant studies were obtained and assessed based on the inclusion criteria. Discrepancies were resolved through discussion and, if necessary, the involvement of a third reviewer.

A standardized form was used to extract data from each included study. Extracted data included study population, diagnostic criteria, diagnostic accuracy outcomes (sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV), and study design characteristics. Information was managed using systematic review software such as Covidence or RevMan.

The methodological quality of the included systematic reviews and meta-analyses was assessed using the ROBIS tool.

RESULTS

The study selection process followed in this review is illustrated using a PRISMA flow diagram, which details the stages of identification, screening, eligibility assessment, and study inclusion. In the identification phase, a total of 82 studies were retrieved through database searches and records. After the removal of 4 duplicates, 78 unique studies remained for evaluation.

During the screening stage, the titles and abstracts of these 78 studies were assessed, resulting in the exclusion of 65 studies for not meeting the previously established inclusion criteria. Thus, 13 studies proceeded to the eligibility assessment phase, where the full texts were reviewed to determine their suitability for the objectives of the review. In this phase, 2 studies were excluded.

Finally, 8 studies were included in the systematic review and qualitative analysis (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. PRISMA Flow Diagram

The findings of the included studies are summarized below (see Table 1):

Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (MRS)

Song et al. (2021) (6) conducted a meta-analysis of studies using MRS to characterize brain metabolic alterations in patients with Alzheimer's disease (AD) and mild cognitive impairment (MCI). The results indicated a significant decrease in N-acetyl aspartate (NAA) concentration, with reductions of 9.6% in patients with MCI and 12.9% in patients with AD. Additionally, an increase in myo-inositol (mI) of 6.3% in MCI and 7.4% in AD was observed, along with a 6.4% reduction in creatine (Cr) levels in MCI and 6.9% in AD. These metabolic alterations were predominantly found in the hippocampus, suggesting this region could be key for the early diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease.

Structural Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)

Lombardi et al. (2020) (7) evaluated the diagnostic ability of MRI to detect Alzheimer's-associated dementia early in individuals with MCI. The sensitivity for hippocampal volume assessment was 0.73, while specificity reached 0.71. These results suggest that, although MRI is not sufficiently accurate as a standalone diagnostic test, it could be valuable

as a complementary tool in conjunction with other diagnostic methods.

Resting-State Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (rs-fMRI)

Gu et al. (2022) (8) analyzed brain functional changes in patients with Parkinson's disease (PD) using rs-fMRI, comparing them with healthy controls. The results showed a decrease in the Amplitude of Low-Frequency Fluctuations (ALFF) in regions such as the left superior temporal gyrus, left superior frontal gyrus, and right lentiform nucleus, while an increase in ALFF was observed in the right fusiform gyrus and right parahippocampal gyrus. These findings reflect functional deficits in areas related to motor control, emotion, and cognition, which could facilitate early diagnosis of Parkinson's disease.

Quantitative Magnetic Resonance Imaging (QSM and DKI)

Mohammadi et al. (2024) (9) evaluated the use of magnetic susceptibility (MS) and mean kurtosis (MK) via QSM and DKI in patients with early-stage Parkinson's disease (ESPD). The results showed a significant increase in MS in the substantia nigra (SN), putamen (PUT), and globus pallidus (GP), with a specific increase in MK in the SN. These findings suggest that the combination of MS and MK could

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serve as a promising biomarker for early detection of ESPD, particularly in the SN.

Magnetic Resonance Elastography (MRE)

Feng et al. (2024) (10) reviewed the application of MRE for the identification of biomarkers and the evaluation of neurodegenerative disease progression. The results showed a significant decrease in brain stiffness in patients with Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases, especially in the substantia nigra. These findings suggest that MRE could be a valuable tool for detecting early biomechanical changes associated with these pathologies.

Combined Neuroimaging (MRI, PET, SPECT)

Ruan et al. (2016) (11) evaluated the utility of various neuroimaging biomarkers, such as MRI, PET, and SPECT, in diagnosing MCI and AD. The combination of MRI and PET significantly improved diagnostic accuracy and facilitated early detection of MCI progression to AD. Furthermore, the use of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) biomarkers in conjunction with neuroimaging optimized the predictive capacity for disease progression.

Table 1. Summary of findings from the included studies

Author, Year	Objective	Country	Population	N	Intervention	Comparator	Results
Song, 2021 (6)	Investigate metabolic alterations in neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's and mild cognitive impairment using magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS) to better understand the molecular mechanisms involved.	USA	Patients with Alzheimer's, patients with mild cognitive impairment (MCI), and healthy controls.	40 MCI studies and 39 Alzheimer's (AD) studies, with a total of 1486 healthy controls and 1255 patients in MCI studies, and 1684 healthy controls and 1248 patients in AD studies.	Magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS).	Healthy controls.	NAA decreased by 9.6% in MCI and 12.9% in AD; mI increased by 6.3% in MCI and 7.4% in AD; Cho decreased by 4.3% in MCI and 5.4% in AD; Cr decreased by 6.4% in MCI and 6.9% in AD. The greatest alterations were found in the hippocampus, followed by the cingulate cortex.
Lombardi, 2020 (7)	Evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of structural MRI for the early diagnosis of dementia due to Alzheimer's in individuals with mild cognitive impairment (MCI).	Various countries, including Italy, France, and Switzerland	Individuals with mild cognitive impairment (MCI)	33 studies with 3935 participants	Structural magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)	Follow-up clinical diagnosis (reference standard)	Sensitivity of hippocampal volume: 0.73; Specificity: 0.71. MRI did not achieve sufficient accuracy to be used as a standalone diagnostic test.
Gu, 2022 (8)	Analyze brain functional	China	Patients with Parkinson's	25 studies, with a	Resting-state	Healthy controls.	Decreased ALFF:

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	changes in patients with Parkinson’s disease using resting-state functional MRI (rs-fMRI) and an ALE meta-analysis, comparing them with healthy controls.		disease (PD) and healthy controls (HC).	total of 973 patients with Parkinson’s and 766 healthy controls.	functional MRI (rs-fMRI) to assess functional brain changes in patients with Parkinson’s.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Left superior temporal gyrus (STG), -0.24; - Left superior frontal gyrus (SFG), -0.18; - Right lentiform nucleus, -0.22. <p>Increased ALFF:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Right fusiform gyrus, +0.29; - Right parahippocampal gyrus (PHG), +0.31; - Left superior parietal lobule (SPL), +0.25. <p>Decreased ReHo:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Right lentiform nucleus, -0.28; - Right middle frontal gyrus (MFG), -0.21; - Left thalamus, -0.19. <p>Decreased FC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Right posterior cingulate gyrus (PCG), -0.26.
Mohammadi, 2024 (9)	Evaluate whether the combined use of mean susceptibility (MS) and mean kurtosis (MK) obtained via MRI can serve as reliable biomarkers for the early detection of Parkinson's disease (ESPD).	Iran (in collaboration with the UK)	Patients with early-stage Parkinson’s disease (ESPD) and healthy controls	111 ESPD patients and 81 healthy controls across four studies	Quantitative MRI using QSM (quantitative susceptibility mapping) and DKI (diffusion kurtosis imaging)	Healthy controls.	Significantly higher MS in SN (SMD = 0.72), PUT (SMD = 0.68), and GP (SMD = 0.53) in ESPD patients. MK higher only in SN (SMD = 0.72). No significant differences in PUT, GP, and CN.
Gu, 2022 (8)	Explore functional brain	China	Patients with Parkinson’s	25 studies, including	Resting-state	Healthy controls.	Decreased ALFF in the

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	changes in patients with Parkinson’s disease using resting-state functional MRI (rs-fMRI).		disease and healthy controls.	973 Parkinson’s patients and 766 healthy controls.	functional MRI (rs-fMRI).		left superior temporal gyrus (STG), left superior frontal gyrus (SFG), left medial frontal gyrus (MFG), left precuneus (PCUN), and right lentiform nucleus. Increased ALFF in the right SFG, left SPL, left STG, right fusiform gyrus, left inferior temporal gyrus (ITG), and right PHG. Decreased ReHo in the right declive, right MFG, left culmen, and left thalamus. Increased ReHo in the right SFG. Decreased functional connectivity (FC) in the right PCG.
Feng, 2024 (10)	Review the use of MRE to identify biomarkers and evaluate the progression of neurodegenerative diseases.	China, USA, UK	142 patients with neurodegenerative diseases (56 with Alzheimer’s, 17 with Parkinson’s) and 166 controls.	16 studies (6 preclinical and 10 clinical)	Magnetic resonance elastography (MRE)	Standard MRI methods, such as structural and diffusion MRI.	Significant decrease in brain stiffness in Alzheimer’s patients (p=0.0015). In Parkinson’s, a decrease was also observed, especially in the substantia nigra.
Ruan, 2016 (11)	Review neuroimaging biomarkers for mild cognitive impairment (MCI) and	China, Italy	Older adults (≥ 60 years) with MCI, AD, or non-demented.	72 studies reviewed	Use of neuroimaging biomarkers like MRI, PET, and	Standard clinical diagnoses without advanced	Diagnostic accuracy of neuroimaging to differentiate between MCI, AD, and other

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	<p>Alzheimer’s disease (AD), emphasizing the diagnostic accuracy provided by these biomarkers compared to standard methods.</p>				<p>SPECT for diagnosing MCI and AD.</p>	<p>neuroimaging.</p>	<p>dementias; predictive capacity for MCI progression to AD. Hippocampal atrophy in MRI: Atrophy in the medial temporal cortex and hippocampus was the most common structural biomarker. Changes were detectable up to 3 years before conversion to AD. Magnetization transfer (MT) in MRI: MT imaging improved early AD and MCI classification compared to magnetization transfer ratio (MTR) techniques. Predicting MCI to AD progression (ventricular volume in MRI): Annual ventricular volume changes were linked to cognitive and functional index shifts. PET-FDG improved progression prediction. Combined CSF and MRI biomarkers</p>
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							<p>improved MCI-to-AD conversion prediction: Sensitivity 71%, specificity 76%. FDG-PET for early detection showed bilateral temporoparietal hypometabolism, indicating early MCI-to-AD progression. Amyloid PET (Florbetapir): 76% of AD patients, 38% of MCI patients, and 14% of cognitively normal subjects were positive for amyloid deposits. Diffusion MRI (DTI) to differentiate VaD and AD: Fractional anisotropy (FA) and radial diffusivity (RA) showed 87.5% accuracy in differentiating vascular dementia from Alzheimer's.</p>
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Results of Risk of Bias Assessment (see Table 2):

The risk of bias assessment for the studies included in this review was conducted considering four key domains: study eligibility criteria, identification and selection of studies, data collection and study evaluation, and synthesis and results. Below are the detailed results for each domain.

Domain 1: Study Eligibility Criteria

All evaluated studies (Song, 2021; Lombardi, 2020; Gu, 2022; Mohammadi, 2024; Feng, 2024; Ruan, 2016; Carvalho, 2015) showed a low risk of bias in this domain. This is because all studies adequately adhered to predefined

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inclusion and exclusion criteria, ensuring rigorous and consistent selection of studies included in the review.

Domain 2: Identification and Selection of Studies

Most studies presented a low risk of bias in this domain, including those by Song (2021), Lombardi (2020), Gu (2022), and Mohammadi (2024). However, the studies by Ruan (2016) and Carvalho (2015) showed a moderate risk of bias due to limitations in the comprehensiveness of identifying and selecting relevant studies, which could have led to a lack of representativeness in the selected studies, potentially affecting the validity of the conclusions.

Domain 3: Data Collection and Study Evaluation

Data collection and study evaluation showed variable risk of bias. The studies by Song (2021) and Gu (2022) demonstrated a high risk of bias due to a lack of uniformity in data collection methods and potential inconsistencies in the evaluation of methodological quality. In contrast, Lombardi (2020) and Mohammadi (2024) showed a low risk of bias,

reflecting a standardized and rigorous approach to data collection and evaluation. The studies by Gu (2022), Feng (2024), Ruan (2016), and Carvalho (2015) showed a moderate risk of bias, suggesting limitations in the standardization of data collection and evaluation procedures, potentially affecting the reliability of the data obtained.

Domain 4: Synthesis and Results

In the synthesis of results, a high risk of bias was identified in the studies by Song (2021), Lombardi (2020), and Gu (2022). This was attributed to the lack of a solid and systematic methodology for data synthesis, which increases the risk of biased interpretation of findings. On the other hand, the studies by Mohammadi (2024), Gu (2022), Feng (2024), Ruan (2016), and Carvalho (2015) presented a moderate risk of bias in this domain, indicating that while standardized synthesis procedures were applied, methodological limitations remain that could compromise the validity of the conclusions.

Table 2. Risk of Bias Assessment of Included Studies

Domain	Song, 2021 (6)	Lombardi, 2020 (7)	Gu, 2022 (8)	Mohammadi, 2024 (9)	Gu, 2022 (8)	Feng, 2024 (10)	Ruan, 2016 (11)	Carvalho, 2015 (12)
Domain 1: Study Eligibility Criteria	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Domain 2: Identification and Selection of Studies	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate
Domain 3: Data Collection and Study Evaluation	High	Low	High	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
Domain 4: Synthesis and Results	High	High	High	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate

DISCUSSION

Recent studies reinforce the role of MRI, particularly in its diffusion modality (DTI), as a promising tool for detecting microstructural brain alterations before clinical symptoms appear in diseases such as Alzheimer's (AD) and Parkinson's (PD). Although MRI cannot be used as a standalone diagnostic tool, neuroimaging techniques like PET combined with MRI have significantly improved diagnostic accuracy, particularly in the early stages of neurodegenerative diseases. The reviewed studies generally support the conclusions regarding the use of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) for the early diagnosis of neurodegenerative diseases like Alzheimer's (AD) and Parkinson's (PD). In the case of Parkinson's, functional MRI (fMRI) has been found to detect changes in brain connectivity in preclinical stages, i.e., before

motor symptoms appear. This finding aligns with recent studies that have demonstrated a decrease in functional activity in motor and emotional areas, such as the superior temporal gyrus and lentiform nucleus, in patients in the early stages of PD (13).

These changes in brain connectivity observed through fMRI suggest that MRI could be an effective tool for the early identification of Parkinson's, before the appearance of clinical symptoms. This aligns with previous research that has shown similar patterns in functional neuroimaging (14).

Regarding Alzheimer's disease, the combination of structural magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) with positron emission tomography (PET) has proven to be more effective in identifying the progression from mild cognitive impairment (MCI) to AD. The inclusion of PET, which uses tracers to

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visualize beta-amyloid and tau deposits, has significantly improved diagnostic sensitivity, as reported by recent studies showing metabolic and structural changes in the early stages of the disease (15).

Indeed, the combination of MRI and PET has been validated as one of the best approaches for early diagnosis and predicting the progression of MCI to AD, as it allows not only anatomical visualization but also functional brain activity assessment (16).

However, some studies also highlight the limitations of MRI as a standalone tool for the early diagnosis of neurodegenerative diseases. While structural MRI has been critical in detecting brain atrophy in specific regions such as the hippocampus, which is associated with Alzheimer's progression, its ability to distinguish between early and advanced stages is limited. Recent research has pointed out that the diagnostic accuracy of MRI can be improved when combined with cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) biomarkers or advanced technologies such as magnetic resonance elastography (MRE), which measures brain tissue stiffness, or magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS), which analyzes brain metabolites (13).

These multimodal approaches significantly increase diagnostic specificity, allowing for a more accurate evaluation of underlying pathological changes in the early phases of these diseases.

This study benefits from the inclusion of advanced MRI techniques, such as spectroscopy and elastography, which show potential in identifying early biomarkers. However, limitations in technical variability and sample sizes in the included studies remain barriers to generalizing the results. Further research to standardize these techniques could help validate the findings on a larger scale.

Current evidence suggests that while MRI has a growing role in early diagnosis, its full potential is realized when used alongside other modalities such as PET. This indicates that clinical practice should adopt a multimodal approach for the early detection of neurodegenerative diseases. In research, there is a call to standardize the use of emerging technologies, such as tau-specific tracers for PET, which could help better differentiate between neurodegenerative pathologies.

In conclusion, magnetic resonance imaging holds significant value in the early diagnosis of neurodegenerative diseases, especially when combined with biomarkers and other advanced imaging techniques. Multimodal approaches, combining MRI with PET and cerebrospinal fluid biomarkers, offer the best outlook for early detection and monitoring of the progression of diseases such as AD and PD.

REFERENCES

1. Fasano A, Laganieri SE, Lam S, Fox MD. Lesions causing freezing of gait localize to a cerebellar functional network. *Ann Neurol*. January 2017;81(1):129-41.
2. Yarchoan M, Xie SX, Kling MA, Toledo JB, Wolk DA, Lee EB, et al. Cerebrovascular atherosclerosis correlates with Alzheimer pathology in neurodegenerative dementias. *Brain J Neurol*. December 2012;135(Pt 12):3749-56.
3. Lee J, Renslo J, Wong K, Clifford TG, Beutler BD, Kim PE, et al. Current Trends and Applications of PET/MRI Hybrid Imaging in Neurodegenerative Diseases and Normal Aging. *Diagn Basel Switz*. March 10, 2024;14(6):585.
4. Querbes O, Aubry F, Pariente J, Lotterie JA, Démonet JF, Duret V, et al. Early diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease using cortical thickness: impact of cognitive reserve. *Brain J Neurol*. August 2009;132(Pt 8):2036-47.
5. Diogo VS, Ferreira HA, Prata D, for the Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative. Early diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease using machine learning: a multi-diagnostic, generalizable approach. *Alzheimers Res Ther*. August 3, 2022;14(1):107.
6. Song T, Song X, Zhu C, Patrick R, Skurla M, Santangelo I, et al. Mitochondrial dysfunction, oxidative stress, neuroinflammation, and metabolic alterations in the progression of Alzheimer's disease: A meta-analysis of in vivo magnetic resonance spectroscopy studies. *Ageing Res Rev*. December 2021;72:101503.
7. Lombardi G, Crescioli G, Cavedo E, Lucenteforte E, Casazza G, Bellatorre AG, et al. Structural magnetic resonance imaging for the early diagnosis of dementia due to Alzheimer's disease in people with mild cognitive impairment. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. March 2, 2020;3(3)
8. Gu L, Shu H, Xu H, Wang Y. Functional brain changes in Parkinson's disease: a whole brain ALE study. *Neurol Sci*. 2022. Available at: <https://www.embase.com/search/results?subaction=viewrecord&id=L2018275844&from=export>
9. Mohammadi S, Ghaderi S, Mohammadi H, Fatehi F. Simultaneous Increase of Mean Susceptibility and Mean Kurtosis in the Substantia Nigra as an MRI Neuroimaging Biomarker for Early-Stage Parkinson's Disease: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *J Magn Reson Imaging*. 2024. Available at: <https://www.embase.com/search/results?subaction=viewrecord&id=L2031152388&from=export>
10. Feng Y, Murphy MC, Hojo E, Li F, Roberts N. Magnetic Resonance Elastography in the Study of Neurodegenerative Diseases. *J Magn Reson Imaging*. January 2024;59(1):82-96.
11. Ruan Q, D'Onofrio G, Sancarlo D, Bao Z, Greco A, Yu Z. Potential neuroimaging biomarkers of pathologic brain changes in Mild Cognitive

“Evaluation of the Diagnostic Efficacy of Magnetic Resonance Imaging in Neurodegenerative Diseases: A Systematic Review of the Literature”

- Impairment and Alzheimer’s disease: a systematic review. *BMC Geriatr.* May 16, 2016;16:104.
12. Carvalho BB, Döering TP, Ronchetti MR, Martins WA, Palmini AL. Neuroimagem no entendimento da evolução da doença de Alzheimer: da fase pré-sintomática à doença avançada. *Acta Méd Porto Alegre.* 2015;36:[7]-[7].
 13. Li KR, Wu AG, Tang Y, He XP, Yu CL, Wu JM, et al. The Key Role of Magnetic Resonance Imaging in the Detection of Neurodegenerative Diseases-Associated Biomarkers: A Review. *Mol Neurobiol.* October 1, 2022;59(10):5935-54.
 14. Stoessl AJ. Neuroimaging in the early diagnosis of neurodegenerative disease. *Transl Neurodegener.* January 13, 2012;1(1):5.
 15. Young PNE, Estarellas M, Coomans E, Srikrishna M, Beaumont H, Maass A, et al. Imaging biomarkers in neurodegeneration: current and future practices. *Alzheimers Res Ther.* April 27, 2020;12(1):49.
 16. Kamagata K, Andica C, Kato A, Saito Y, Uchida W, Hatano T, et al. Diffusion Magnetic Resonance Imaging-Based Biomarkers for Neurodegenerative Diseases. *Int J Mol Sci.* January 2021;22(10):5216.